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EFFECT OF *AUMKARA MANTRA* MEDITATION ON MENTAL HEALTH: A REVIEW STUDY

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Abstract

Introduction: People who are in a state of mental well-being are able to manage life's stress, tap into their abilities, learn and work effectively and make positive contributions to society. In the present era, due to bad/disturbed lifestyle, mental health issues have become a big global burden so far as the diseases are concerned. As per the description found from ancient literature and studies done from contemporary period depict that *Mantras* are effective in addressing the mental health issues. *Mantra* occupies a prominent place in ancient culture, rituals and traditions since the *Vedic* period especially in *Bharata*. Since time immemorial *Rishis* and *Yogis* have been practicing *Mantra Yoga* for spiritual enlightenment. *Aumkara Mantra* is most effective and also known as the "*Pranava*". It is widely chanted during spiritual practices and meditation, revered for its profound impact on physical, mental and spiritual well-being. **Aim:** To assess the effect of *Aumkara Mantra* Meditation on mental health. **Objective:** To elaborate the textual and scientific review of *Aumkara Mantra* meditation and its effect on mental health. **Materials & Method:** All available classical *Yogic* texts like *Patanjala Yoga Sutra*, *Bhagvadgeeta*, *Upanishads* like *Naadabindu*, *Dhyānbindu*, *Mandukya*, *Taittiriya*, etc. and nine other different databases, were systematically searched and reviewed. **Result & Discussion:** Total 18 studies have been done and registered on *Aumkara Mantra* meditation till date. Among these, seven studies focused on mental health and showed that *Aumkara Mantra* meditation decreases stress levels by enhancing Galvanic Skin Response, reducing psychological distress and more. **Conclusion:** *Aumkara Mantra* is a non-invasive and cost-effective *Yogic* and spiritual practice to promote mental health, improve quality of life by reducing stress level and relieve from all type of miseries to attain salvation. Various studies support that it is effective in decreasing stress levels, enhancing the quality-of-life (QOL) in young woman with PCOS.

Key Words:

Aumkara Chanting, *Mantra*, Meditation, Mental well-being, Health, *Yoga*

INTRODUCTION:

A healthy mental state is an integral part of good Health. According to WHO: "Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity".¹ Mental Health is more than the absence of mental disorders or disabilities. It is a state of mental well-being that enables people to cope with the stresses of life, realize their abilities, learn well and work well, and contribute to their community.² 1 in every 8 people in the world wide suffers from mental disorder.³ WHO estimates that the burden of mental health problems in India is 2443 people disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) per 10,000 population.⁴

Mantra has also been defined as '*Mananat traayate iti Mantrah*' the one which saves or protects on being contemplated upon is a *Mantra*. A "*Mantra*" is a sacred utterance, a numinous sound, a syllable, word or phonemes, or group of words in Sanskrit believed by practitioners to have psychological and spiritual powers. *Mantra* took a central position in various rituals. Gradually, with the advent of *Tantra*, it became a main tool for it as well. It is believed that the language gradually developed from the *MAHESHWAR SUTRAS* - the drumming sound of Lord *Shiva* - *Nruttavasane Natarajarajo Ninad Dhakkam Navapanchavaram*. It is also believed that there prevailed the primordial sound even before the creation and that shall exist even after nothing remains. That sound is believed to be *Pranava* or *AUM* and hence it has been referred to as *MANTRA RAJ*.⁵

The *Aumkara Mantra* consisting of the three letters A, U, and M converting the whole process of articulation has shown to enhance parasympathetic nervous system Stimulation.⁶ *Patanjala Yoga Sutra* is one of the classical *Yoga* texts in which the *Pranava* (AUM) has explained and denoted the word '*Ishwara*'. There is one of the important tool towards the "*Yogas Chitta Vritti Nirodhah*".⁷ Meditation on AUM with feeling and meaning leads to realisation of Self.⁸ In recent times, scientific research on the *Aumkara Mantra* has significantly increased, with numerous studies highlighting its beneficial impacts on mental health.

AIM:

To assess the effect of *Aumkara Mantra* Meditation on mental health.

OBJECTIVE:

To elaborate the textual and scientific review of *Aumkara Mantra* meditation and its effect on mental health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

All available classical *Yogic* texts like *Patanjala Yoga Sutra*, *Upanishads* like *Mandukya*, *Taittiriya*, *Dhyandindu*, *Nadabindu* etc. have been thoroughly reviewed for the current review paper. *Different databases, such as PubMed, Research Gate, Google Scholar, Science Direct, Scopus, J-Gate, AYU Journal, Dhara, Ayush Research Portal* were also searched using key words like *AUM/OM meditation*,

Aumkara/OM Mantra, Aumkara Mantra meditation, Mantra meditation, Aumkara/OM Mantra meditation on mental health, Mantra meditation on mental health with the help of Boolean operators like "AND", "OR" and "Not". A total of 269 articles were found on Google Scholar, 12 on PubMed, 2 in the Ayu Journal, 100 on Research Gate, and 314 on J-Gate. No articles were found in Science Direct, Scopus, Dhara and the Ayush Research Portal. After excluding duplicates and unrelated articles, 18 were retained. However, 2 studies were excluded due to the unavailability of the full text. Ultimately, 16 studies were found to be related to *Aumkara Mantra* meditation, out of which 7 studies focused on mental health and were included in this review.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

- 1. Patanjala Yoga Sutra:** In the *Patanjala Yoga Sutra*, there is a single direct mention about *Pranava* (*AUM/OM*). That is तस्य वाचकः प्रणवः॥ Its manifestation of *Ishvara* in the form of sound (and letter) form is *Pranava* or *AUMkara*.⁹ In another verse explains that the representation of *Ishvara*, that is तज्जपस्तदर्थभावनम् ॥ it is continuous and repeated recitation of *Pranava/ Aumkara* with meditation on its meaning.¹⁰
- 2. Gheranda Samhita:**
तन्मध्ये कर्णिकायां तु अकथादिरेखात्रयम् । In the centre, *Karnika* (within the core), there are three lines starting with the syllables 'A', 'Ka' and 'Tha', forming a triangle shape. ह ल क्ष कोण संयुक्तं प्रणवं तत्रवर्तते । that means the symbolic *Shabda*(Sound), of the angles of this triangle are *Ham, Lam* and *Ksham*. Inside that triangle, in the centre, the sacred syllable '*AUM/OM*' (*Pranava*) is present.¹¹
भ्रुवोर्मध्ये मनोर्ध्वे च यत्तेजः प्रणवात्मकम् । The *Mantra AUM/OM*, full of light, is located beyond the brain in the eyebrow centre. ध्यायेज्ज्वालावलीयुक्तं तेजोध्यानं तदेव हि । This *Pranava* is the symbol of the soul or self. Meditation on this bright illuminating light is known as *Pranava Dhyana*.¹²
- 3. Dhyandbindu Upanishad:**

TABLE NO. 01- THE FORM OF THE PRANAVA ¹³

S. N.	Akara (A)	Ukara (U)	Makara (M)
1.	Prithvi	Antariksha	Dyur
2.	Agni	Vayu	Surya
3.	Rigveda	Yajurveda	Samveda
4.	Bhuh	Bhuvah	Svah
5.	Brahma	Vishnu	Mahesh
6.	Pita (Yellow Colour)	Shukla (White colour)	Krishna (Dark colour)
7.	Rajoguna	Sattvikaguna	Tamasguna

One who does not know *AUMkara/Omkara* as having eight *Angas* (Parts), Four *Padas* (Feet), Three *Sthana* (Seats) and five *Devatas* (Presiding deities) is not a *Brahmana*.¹⁴

TABLE NO. 02-PRANAVA, ATMA, BRAHMAN: THE DIVINE TRIAD¹⁵

S. N.	AUMkara/OMkara	
1.	Pranava	Dhanu (Bow)
2.	Atma	Shara (Arrow)
3.	Brahman	Lakshya (Aim)

Rule for Meditation on the Pranava

One should aim at it with great care and then one, like the arrow, becomes one with It. When that highest is cognised, all Karmas return (from one, viz., do not affect one).¹⁶

The Vedas have AUMkara/OMkara as their cause. The Svaras (sounds) have AUMkara/OMkara as their cause. The three worlds with (all) the locomotive and the fixed (ones in them) have AUMkara/OMkara as their cause. The short (accent of AUM/OM) burns all sins, the long one is decay less and the bestower of prosperity. United with Ardhamatra (half-metre of AUM/OM), the Pranava becomes the bestower of salvation. That man is the knower of the Vedas who knows that the end (viz., Ardhamatra) of Pranava should be worshipped (or recited) as uninterrupted as the flow of oil and (resounding) as long as the sound of a bell.¹⁷

Pranava Dhyana with Pranayama:

One should contemplate/meditate upon AUMkara/OMkara as Ishvara resembling an unshaken light, as of the size of a thumb and as motionless in the middle of the pericarp of the lotus of the heart.¹⁸

Taking in Vayu through the left nostril (Ida) and filling the stomach with it, one should contemplate/meditate upon AUMkara/OMkara as being in the middle of the body and as surrounded by circling flames.¹⁹

These are the Devatas of Pranayama

Brahma is said to be Puraka (inspiration);

Vishnu is said to be Kumbhaka (cessation) (of breath), and

Rudra is said to be Rechaka (expiration).²⁰

Pranava Dhyana with different method:

Having made Atman as the (lower) Arani (sacrificial wood) and Pranava as the upper Arani, one should see the God in secret through the practice of churning which is Dhyana. One should practise restraint of breath as much as it lies in one's power along with (the uttering of) AUMkara/OMkara sound, until it ceases completely.²¹

Those who look upon AUM/OM as of the form of Hamsa staying in all, shining like crores of suns, being alone, staying in Gamagama (ever going and coming) and being devoid of motion at last such persons are freed from sin.²²

Meditation on the Qualified Brahman:

*That Manas which is the author of the actions (viz.), Srushti (creation), Sthiti (preservation) and Vilaya (destruction) of the three worlds, is (then) absorbed (in the supreme One). That is the highest state of Vishnu.*²³

*The lotus of the heart has eight petals and thirty-two filaments. The sun is in its midst: the moon is in the middle of the sun. Agni is in the middle of the moon the Prabha (spiritual light) is in the middle of Agni. Pitha (seat or centre) is in the midst of Prabha, being set in diverse gems. One should meditate upon the stainless Lord Vasudeva as being (seated) upon the centre of Pitha, as having Shrivatsa (black mark) and Kaustubha (garland of gems) on his chest and as adorned with gems and pearls resembling pure crystal in lustre and as resembling crores of moons in brightness.*²⁴

Meditation on the Brahma, Maha-Vishnu & Shiva:

*One should meditate upon Maha-Vishnu as above or in the following manner. (That is) one should meditate with inspiration (of breath) upon Maha-Vishnu as resembling the Atasi flower and as staying in the seat of navel with four hands; then with restraint of breath, one should meditate in the heart upon Brahma, the Grandfather as being on the lotus with the Gaura (pale-red) colour of gems and having four faces: then through expiration, he should meditate upon the three-eyed Shiva between the two eyebrows shining like the pure crystal, being stainless, destroying all sins.*²⁵

Meditation in the Heart and its fruit:

*Being in that which is like the lotus facing down with its flower (or face) below and the stalk above or like the flower of a plantain tree, being of the form of all Vedas, containing one hundred petals and one hundred leaves and having the pericarp full-expanded. There one should meditate upon the sun, the moon and the Agni, one above another. Passing above through lotus which has the brightness of the sun, moon and Agni, and taking its Hrīm Bija (letter), one leads one's Atma firmly.*²⁶

*One is the knower of Vedas who knows the three seats, the three Matras, the three Brahmas, the three Aksharas (letters) and the three Matras associated with the Ardhamatra. One who knows that which is above Bindu, Nada and Kala as uninterrupted as the flow of oil and (resounding) as long as the sound of a bell- that man is a knower of the Vedas.*²⁷

4. Naadabindu Upanishad

**TABLE NO. 03 - AUM/OM: THIS ATMAN IS BIRD (HAMSA) & ITS BODY PARTS
CORRELATE WITH AUM/OM²⁸**

<i>A (Akara)</i>	<i>Dakshina Paksha (Right wing)</i>
<i>U (Ukara)</i>	<i>Vama Paksha (Left wing)</i>
<i>M (Makara)</i>	<i>Puccha (Tail-feather)</i>

<i>Ardhamatra (Half mora)</i>	<i>Mastaka (Head)</i>
<i>Rajas and Tamas</i>	<i>Pada (Feet)</i>
<i>Sattva</i>	<i>Sharira (Body)</i>
<i>Dharma (Righteousness)</i>	<i>Dakshina Chakshu (Right eye)</i>
<i>Adharma (wrong)</i>	<i>Vama Chakshu (Left eye)</i>
<i>Bhurloka</i>	<i>Pada (Feet)</i>
<i>Bhuvarloka</i>	<i>Janu (Knee)</i>
<i>Sarvaloka</i>	<i>Katipradesha (Loins)</i>
<i>Maharloka</i>	<i>Nabhipradesha (Navel region)</i>
<i>Janaloka</i>	<i>Hrud desha (Heart)</i>
<i>Tapoloka</i>	<i>Kantha (Neck)</i>
<i>Satyaloka</i>	<i>Bhru-lalat-Madhye (center of the forehead between the eyebrows)</i>

TABLE NO. 04 - MATRA OF AUM/OM

S.N.	Aumkara		
	1 st Matra	2 nd Matra	3 rd Matra
1. Tri Matra	Aagneyi	Vayavya	Bhanumandal Sankasha (Lustre of the solar orb)
2. Ardhamatra	Varuna		

Each of these Matras has indeed three Kalas (parts). This is called AUMkara/OMkara. ²⁹

TABLE NO. 05 NAME OF TWELVE DIFFERENT MATRAS AND THEIR BENEFITS DERIVED BY VOTARIES ON THEIR DYING DURING PARTICULAR MATRAS ³⁰

S. N.	Matras	Dhyana benefits
1.	<i>Ghoshini (Rich in sound)</i>	<i>Dying in Ghoshini Matra, he is born as a sovereign king in Bharata Varsha.</i>
2.	<i>Vidyunmali (Wreathed with lightning)</i>	<i>Death in Vidyunmali Matra, he becomes Maha-Atmavan (an illustrious) Yaksha</i>
3.	<i>Patangini (Flight-enjoyer)</i>	<i>Departing in Patangini Matra, becomes a Vidhyadhara</i>
4.	<i>Vayuvegini (Swift as wind)</i>	<i>Dying in Vayuvegini Matra, becomes a Gandharva.</i>
5.	<i>Namadheya (Namable)</i>	<i>Death in Namadheya Matra, viz., Ardhamatra, he lives among gods and roams in the Somaloka (region of moon) magnificently.</i>
6.	<i>Aindri (Belonging to Indra)</i>	<i>Death in Aindri Matra, he merges into Indra.</i>
7.	<i>Vaishnavi (Belong to Vishnu)</i>	<i>Death in Vaishnavi Matra, he reaches at the seat of Vishnu</i>
8.	<i>Shankari (After Shankara)</i>	<i>Attains Rudra, the lord of all creatures, happens upon passing in Shankari Matra.</i>

9.	<i>Mahati (Great)</i>	<i>Death in Mahati Matra leads to Maharloka</i>
10.	<i>Dhruti (Regarding to firmness)</i>	<i>Death in Dhruti Matra leads to Janaloka</i>
11.	<i>Nari (Women)</i>	<i>Death in Nari Matra leads to Tapoloka</i>
12.	<i>Brahmi (The Brahmic)</i>	<i>Dying in Brahmi Mudra attains the eternal state of Brahma</i>

Technique for inner sound meditation:

*The Yogi being in Siddhasana and practicing Vaishnavi Mudra, should always hear the internal sound (Nada) through the right ear.*³¹

5. Mandukya Upanishad

All is OM: OM! This Imperishable Word is the whole of this visible universe. Its explanation is as follows: What has become, what is becoming, what will become – verily, all of this is OM. And what is beyond these three states of the world of time – that too, verily, is OM.³²

Atman has Four Aspects: All this, verily, is *Brahman*. The Self is *Brahman*. This Self has four quarters.³³

TABLE NO. 06 – THE FOUR STATES OF CONSCIOUSNESS³⁴

S. N.	State	Quarter	Field	Consciousness	Characteristics	Enjoyment
1.	Waking/ Gross	<i>Vaishvanara</i>	Waking State	Outward-turned	7 limbed, 19-mouthed	Gross objects
2.	Dreaming/ Subtle	<i>Tejas</i>	Dream State	Inward-turned	7 limbed, 19-mouthed	Subtle objects
3.	Deep Sleep/ Causal	<i>Prajna</i>	Dreamless sleep	Undivided, mass of consciousness	Blissful, his mouth is Consciousness	Bliss
4.	<i>Turiya</i>	-	Beyond duality	Neither inward nor outward, nor together, not an in differentiated mass consciousness	Invisible, ineffable, blissful	Self-awareness

Those Four are the Same with “A-U-M” and Silence: This identical *Atman*, or Self, in the realm of sound is the syllable *AUM/OM*, the above described four quarters of the Self being identical with the components of the syllable, and the components of the syllable being identical with the four quarters of the Self. The components of the Syllable are A, U, M.³⁵

TABLE NO. 07 - CORRELATION WITH *AUM/OM* ³⁶

S.N.	Sound	State	Quarter	Characteristics	Benefit of Knowledge
1.	A	<i>Jagrita /Waking/ Gross</i>	<i>Vaishvanara</i>	because this encompasses all, and because it is the first	One who knows thus, encompasses all desirable objects
2.	U	<i>Swapna/Dreaming/Subtle</i>	<i>Tejas</i>	because this is an excellence, and contains the qualities of the other two	One who knows thus, exalts the flow of knowledge and becomes equalised; in his family there will be born no one ignorant of Brahman.
3.	M	<i>Sushupta/Deep Sleep/ Causal</i>	<i>Prajna</i>	because this is the measure, and that into which all enters	One who knows thus, measures all and becomes all.
4.	Silence after "A-U-M"	<i>Turiya</i>	-	The fourth is soundless: unutterable, a quieting down of all relative manifestations, blissful, peaceful, non-dual. Thus, <i>AUM/OM</i> is the <i>Atman</i> , verily	One who knows thus, merges his self in the Self

FIGURE 01 - *AUM/OM* SYMBOL AND THE ELEMENTS OF *MANDUKYA UPANISHAD*:

6. *Taittiriya Upanishad*

The sacred sound *OM* is *Brahman*. All this is the syllable *AUM/OM*.³⁷

7. *Pranava Upanishad*

TABLE NO. 08- THE FORM OF THE PRANAVA³⁸

S.N.	Aumkara			
1.	Tri Matra	A(Akara)	U (Ukara)	M(Makara)
2.	Tri Deva	Brahma	Vishnu	Mahesh
3.	Tri Loka	Bhuh	Bhuvah	Svah
4.	Tri Agni	Garhpatya	Dakshin Agni	Aahavaneeya
5.	Tri Veda	Rigveda	Yajurveda	Samveda
6.	Swaroopa	Suryamandala bhati/Surya	Chandramandala/Soma	Agnitejas
7.	Ardhamatra	Anusvara, Sikha Urdhvagami		

The light of the minutest upper end of the flame analogous to the tube of a lotus is seen in the region of mind. This second flame is located by holding the splendor analogous to the sun from the nostril by penetrating the orbit of the sun.³⁹

The upper flame (the half *mora* of the syllable *AUM/OM*) in garb of the fire provides all living organisms the life through the seventy two thousand *Nadi* (nerves) and it is located by covering all these *Nadi* (nerves).⁴⁰

The devotee attains peace proxy to the emancipation and one listens to the sound analogous to the gong made of bronze at that time. This is the form of the syllable *AUM/OM*. All devotees wish to listen this form with the sound.⁴¹

The devotee who is engrossed in the vibration of the *AUM/OM* Syllable, becomes in the form of *Brahma* himself. It is definite that one attains the immortality at this stage.⁴²

8. *Kshurikopanishad*

The main contents of the *Veda*, as pronounced by the self-born *Brahma* and the spirit embedded within the meaning of element, one should take an appropriate posture in a silent place, the same way as the tortoise shrinks it's all organs within itself. The devotee in the same way put a check on dissolution or the disorganisation of the spirits arising in the mind and heart employing the twelve *Matras* (moras) under reciting *AUMkara/OMkara* gradually.⁴³

9. *Prashnopanishad*

The syllable *AUM* is the both the higher and the lower *Brahma*. Therefore, one who knows it attains, with its support, the one or the other.⁴⁴

If one meditates on one element [namely a], having been instructed by that alone person quickly comes into the earth [after death]. The *Rig* verses lead him to the world of men. There, united with austerity, chastity and faith, one experiences greatness.⁴⁵

If one is united in mind with two elements [namely a + u], person is led by the *Yajus* formulas to the intermediate space, to the world of the moon. Having experienced greatness in the World of the moon, person returns hither again.⁴⁶

Again, one who meditates on the highest person through this syllable *AUM* consisting of three letters (A, U, M) is united with *Tejas* (Brilliance) in the sun. As a snake is freed from its skin, even so, verily, is person freed from *Papman* (sin). One is led by the *Saman* chants to the world of *Brahma*. He beholds the Person that dwells in the body and that is higher than the highest.⁴⁷

The three elements are deadly when employed (mutually intertwined and comprising the death); One after the other, separately. In actions external, internal, or intermediate when they are properly employed, the knower trembles not.⁴⁸

With the *Rig* verses, to this world;

With the *Saman* chants, to the intermediate space;

With the *Yajus* formulas, to that which sages (*Kavi*) recognize;

With the syllable *AUM/OM* in truth as a support, the knower reaches That which is peaceful, unaging, immortal, fearless and supreme.⁴⁹

10. *Amrutanaada Upanishad*

The place and procedure for *OM* chanting:

Seating oneself on the ground on a seat of *Kusha* grass which is pleasant and devoid of all evils, having protected oneself mentally (from all evil influences), uttering *Ratha-Mandala*, assuming either *Padmasana*, *Svastikasana*, or *Bhadrasana* or any other which can be practiced easily, facing the north and closing the nostril with the thumb, one should inspire through the other nostril and retain breath inside and preserve the *Agni* (fire). Then one should think of the sound (*AUM/OM*) alone.⁵⁰

AUM/OM, the one letter is *Brahman*; *AUM/OM* should not be breathed out. Through this divine *Mantra* (*AUM/OM*), it should be done many times to rid himself of impurity.⁵¹

Then as said before, the *Mantra*-knowing wise should regularly meditate, beginning with the navel upwards in the gross, the primary (or less) gross and subtle (states).⁵²

The greatly wise should give up all (sight) seeing across, up or down and should practice *Yoga* always being motionless and without tremor.⁵³

The union as stated (done) by remaining without tremor in the hallow stalk (viz., *Sushumna*) alone is *Dharana*. The *Yoga* with the ordained duration of twelve *Matras* is called (*Dharana*).⁵⁴

That which never decays is *Akshara* (*AUM/OM*) which is without *Ghoshha* (third, fourth and fifth letters from 'K'), consonant, vowel, palatal, guttural, nasal, letter 'R' and sibilants.⁵⁵

Benefits of Focusing on the Sound of "*Pranav*" (*AUM/OM*):

Prithvi (the Earth element) has five *Matras* (or it takes five *Matras* to pronounce *Parthiva-Pranava*), *Varuna* (the Water element) has four *Matras*, *Agni* (the Fire element) has three *Matras*, *Vayu* (the Air element) has two *Matras*.⁵⁶

Akasha (the Space element) has one *Matras*, and half a *Matras* should be contemplated upon. By mastering the mind, one should meditate on the Self within oneself.⁵⁷

11. *Yogachudamani Upanishad*

The *Pranava*-Prayer

Assuming the *Padmasana* posture aright, holding the body and head erect in a line, one should mutter the imperishable *AUMkara/OMkara*, in a secluded spot, with one eyes resting well on the tip of the nose. ^[58]

TABLE 09 - THE MEANING OF THE SEVERAL LIMBS OF THE PRANAVA⁵⁹

S.N.	<i>Aumkara</i>			
1.	<i>Tri Varna</i>	<i>A (Akara)</i>	<i>U (Ukara)</i>	<i>M (Makara)</i>
2.	<i>Tri Veda</i>	<i>Rig</i>	<i>Yajur</i>	<i>Sam</i>
3.	<i>Tri Loka</i>	<i>Bhuh</i>	<i>Bhvah</i>	<i>Svah</i>
4.	<i>Triguna</i>	<i>Sattva</i>	<i>Raja</i>	<i>Tama</i>
5.	<i>Tri Akshara</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>U</i>	<i>M</i>
6.	<i>Avastha (State)</i>	<i>Jagrita</i>	<i>Swapna</i>	<i>Sushupti</i>
7.	<i>Sthana (Location)</i>	<i>Netra (eyes of all living-organisms)</i>	<i>Kantha (Throat)</i>	<i>Hrud (Heart)</i>
8.	<i>Swaroopa</i>	<i>Virat, Vishva and Sthula</i>	<i>Hiranya-garbha, Tejasa and Sukshma</i>	<i>Karana, Avyakruta, Prajna</i>
9.	<i>Nature</i>	<i>Rajsika</i>	<i>Sattvika</i>	<i>Tamsika</i>
10.	<i>Lord</i>	<i>Brahma</i>	<i>Vishnu</i>	<i>Rudra</i>
11.	<i>Colour</i>	<i>Rakta (Red)</i>	<i>Shukla (White)</i>	<i>Krishna (Black)</i>

The omnipresent *Pranava* (the supreme soul) continuously remains reluctant at the time of the consumption of all pleasant states of the living-soul. ⁶⁰

12. Bhagvadgeeta

TABLE 10 – REFERENCES OF AUM/OM⁶¹

S. N.	<i>Adhyay and Shloka Number</i>	<i>About AUM/OM</i>
1.	<i>Adhyay 8, Shloka 13</i>	It is stated that anyone who vibrates the sound 'AUM/OM,' the one syllable which represents the Absolute (<i>Brahman</i>), and remembers Me (<i>Krishna</i>), while leaving the body, achieves the supreme destination
2.	<i>Adhyay 9, Shloka 17</i>	It is stated, "I am the father of this universe, the mother, the supporter and the grandfather. I am what is to be known, the purifier, the syllable 'AUM/OM,' and certainly, I am the <i>Rig Veda, Sama Veda, and Yajur Veda</i> ".

3.	<i>Adhyay 10, Shloka 25</i>	It is stated that among the great sages, I am Bhrgu; among vibrations, I am the sacred syllable 'AUM/OM'
4.	<i>Adhyay 17, Shloka 24</i>	It is stated, 'Therefore, beginning with 'AUM/OM' and indicating thus, the performances of sacrifice, charity, and penance, which are always performed according to scriptural regulation, are practiced by transcendentalists.'

RESEARCHES RELATED TO EFFECT OF *AUMKARA MANTRA* MEDITATION:

Works on *Aumkara Mantra* Meditation in reference to Mental Health

1. A clinical study involving healthy female participants examined the effects of prayer and OM meditation on galvanic skin response (GSR). The results showed a significant increase in GSR values following prayer and meditation, indicating psychophysiological relaxation. Statistical analysis revealed that prayer and meditation significantly affected GSR values, with increased values suggesting relaxation and decreased stress levels.⁶²

2. A case-control study compared autonomic function parameters (heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and GSR) between a group practicing *OM* meditation and a control group sitting with eyes closed. The results demonstrated statistically significant reductions in heart rate, blood pressure, and respiratory rate, accompanied by increased GSR values, indicating parasympathetic nervous system activation and relaxation following *OM* meditation.⁶³

3. EEG study conducted on healthy engineering students for just 30 minutes results in increased theta power and higher theta amplitude in after condition at all regions in comparison to the before the condition of meditation but results were not significant. No significant results were found in any other band. As per other studies, increased theta power is a sign of relaxation.⁶⁴

4. A study involving 20 subjects practicing *OM* meditation for 20 minutes over a month recorded EEG and GSR before and after intervention. The results showed significant increases in alpha EEG and GSR values, suggesting a positive effect on psychophysiological relaxation and decreased stress levels.⁶⁵

5. A study involving 130 persons of treated mild to severe symptoms of COVID-19 as well as under threat for *AUM* meditation for 30 days. The study assessed Respiration Rate (RR), Blood Pressure (BP), Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A), Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) Scale assessed pre and post intervention which shows statistically significant result after intervention including recovery from depression, anxiety and sleep disorder as well as recovery from fluctuation in vital signs Respiratory Rate and Blood Pressure.⁶⁶ Summary of clinical study of *Aumkara Mantra* meditation in reference to Mental Health is depicted in Table no. 11.

TABLE NO.11 - CLINICAL STUDY OF AUMKARA MANTRA MEDITATION IN REFERENCE TO MENTAL HEALTH

S. N.	Author of the Study	Sample size	Inclusion criteria	Meditation Session	Method/ Scales used for assessment	p-value	Significance
1.	Himani Anand et.al.	20 Healthy Female participants	Age:18-24Years, Only Unmarried & Graduate Female who Willing to participate in the study	30 minutes for 3 days upto 1 month (15 min prayer & 15 min OM meditation)	Galvanic Skin Response on Computerized Polygraph.	<0.01	Statistically Highly Significant
2.	Akshay Berad et.al.	30 Healthy Individuals	Age: 18-20 Years, has given written consent, have no acute or chronic illness and previously not on any type of medication	30 minutes daily in evening hours (20 min. meditation and 10 min for relaxation, Mental chanting of OM in trial group & Sitting relaxed with eye closed in control group.	Cardio-respiratory autonomic parameters (HR, SBP, DBP, MAP, GSR, RR) *	For HR p = 0.001, For SBP p = 0.0011, For DBP p = 0.1683, For MAP p = 0.0079, For RR p = 0.0001, For GSR p = 0.0419	HR, SBP - Statistically Highly Significant MAP, RR, GSR DBP – Statistically significant
3.	Bhavna Harné et. al.	23 Healthy Students	Age: 18-22 years, had no meditation training	30 minutes	EEG assessment	For Alpha wave P=0.308, For Beta Wave P=0.748, For Delta Wave p=0.748, For Gamma	Theta wave – Statistically Significant, Alpha, Beta, Gamma, Delta waves- Statistically Not Significant

						Wave p=0.550, For Theta Wave p=0.866	
4.	Himani Anand et. al.	20 Participants	Age: 18-22 years	20 minutes for month	Electrocardiogram (EEG) and Galvanic Skin Response (GSR)	For EEG P value =0.0366 For GSR t value =3.16	EEG- Statically Significant, GSR- Statically Significant,
5.	Dr. M.K. Bimal et.al. [66]	130 Persons	Age group 27 to 65 Years	AUM Meditation for 30 days	RR, BP, Beck Depression Inventory (BDI), Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A), Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) Scale assessed pre and post intervention	For BDI p value = 0.000, For HAM-A p value = 0.000, For PSQI Scale p value = 0.000	RR, BP, BDI scale, HAM-A scale & PSQI scale statistically significant

TABLE NO. 12 REVIEW STUDY OF AUMKARA MANTRA MEDITATION IN REFERENCE TO MENTAL HEALTH

1	Bhavna P. Harne et al. (2019) conducted a survey that includes a large number of papers covering previous research by various researchers, their results, and different techniques adopted to study the effect of OM meditation on human beings. Studies on OM meditation are categorized under four different headings: neuroimaging studies, EEG studies, evoked potential studies and other methods. Moreover, most of the studies are based on mental OM chanting. That research showed significant alleviation in anxiety and depression through OM meditation. ⁶⁷
2	Vibhuti Rao et.al. (2024) studied total 14 previous trial, out of them 9 were randomized controlled trials (RCTs), while the remaining comprised non-RCTs. Out of them, three trials used OM meditation in holistic <i>Yoga</i> therapy, including other components of <i>Yoga</i> , such as asana and pranayama (breathing) practices. In 1 st study, Nidhi et al.'s RCT (90 adolescents with PCOS) showed that 12-week yoga therapy with mantra meditation improved hormonal, metabolic, and psychological outcomes without adverse effects. In 2 nd study, Rao (2018) found that 12-week yoga therapy with mantra meditation reduced HbA1c, ovarian mass, stress,

anxiety, and depression in PCOS patients (18-40 years), with no adverse effects. In 3rd study, Verma (2019) found that 12-week integrated yoga therapy with mantra meditation improved BMI and heart rate variability in newly diagnosed PCOS patients (20-35 years). Outcomes were predominantly assessed in psychological domains (n=11), followed by anthropometric (n=9), quality of life (n=7), and metabolic metrics (n=7). These three studies have fallen under three domains: psychological, quality of life and metabolic metrics. Out of this, the first two study showed significant improvements in HbA1c, ovarian mass, stress, anxiety and depression while the third study showed significant decrease in BMI and improved heart rate variability in PCOS patient.⁶⁸

RESULT & DISCUSSION:

OM meditation played a significant role in promoting psychophysiological relaxation and reducing stress levels by increasing GSR. While GSR is indicative of high workload or stress, it is also a reliable indicator of relaxation when elevated after meditation.⁶⁹ Furthermore, OM meditation is also important for autonomic function parameters such as heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and GSR. The reduction in heart rate and systolic blood pressure can be attributed to the modulation of autonomic activity, with parasympathetic predominance and relatively reduced sympathetic tone. The decrease in respiratory rate can be explained by the altered mental state, reduction in sympathetic activity, or inhibition of neural activity. A marked increase in GSR was observed in individuals during OM meditation compared to non-meditators. It is well-established that skin resistance decreases in states of anxiety or stress and increases during relaxation.⁷⁰ Furthermore, there are 5 major types of brain waves, namely delta (0.5-3 Hz), theta (3-8 Hz), alpha (8-13 Hz), beta (13-40 HZ), and gamma wave (40-100 Hz).⁷¹ It has been reported that all types of brain waves are present in the brain throughout the day. However, one particular type of brain wave, is dominant depending on the state of consciousness. For instance, during deep sleep state, delta waves are highly prominent. Similarly, theta waves represent a state of sleepiness, alpha waves represent resting and quiet state of brain, beta waves are representation of active brain involved in cognition and thinking task and gamma waves are usually found in deep meditative state of mind⁷², and four state of consciousness also mentioned in *Mandukya Upanishad*⁷³ which can be correlate with brain waves as following:

TABLE NO. 13 CORRELATION OF FOUR STATE OF CONSCIOUSNESS WITH BRAIN WAVES

As per <i>Mandukya Upanishad</i>	State of Consciousness	Brain waves
<i>Jagrita</i>	Waking state	Beta
<i>Svapna</i>	Dream state	Theta
<i>Sushupta</i>	Deep sleep	Delta
<i>Turiya</i>	Transcendental/ fourth state	Alpha, Theta, and Delta waves convergence

To a greater extent, OM meditation has shown significant changes in EEG patterns, with wavelet analysis revealing no significant band oscillations after 30 minutes of OM chanting. However, a notable increase in theta power was observed across all brain regions, indicating reduced cortical arousal.⁷⁴ OM meditation has great significant role which shows the relaxation and decrease stress level.⁷⁵ Moreover, *AUM* meditation played a significant role in overcoming depression, Anxiety, sleep disorders and fluctuation in vital signs (respiratory rate and blood pressure), provided significant relief in Beck depression inventory (BDI), Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A) and Pittsburgh Quality Index (PSQI) scale in persons with treated mild to severe covid-19.⁷⁶

TABLE NO. 14 DISCUSSION ON DIFFERENT YOGIC TEXTS & UPANISHAD

Form of Pranava (A, U, M)	<i>Dhyānbindu Upanishad, Pranava Upanishad, Yogachudamani Upanishad</i>
Matra of AUM	<i>Naadabindu Upanishad, Pranava Upanishad, Kshurikopanishad, Amritanaada Upanishad</i>
Veda correlation	<i>Bhagvadgeeta, Yogachudamani Upanishad, Prashnopanishad, Pranava Upanishad, Dhyānbindu Upanishad</i>
Place, procedure & posture	<i>Kshuriko Upanishad, Prashnopanishad</i>
Four States of consciousness	<i>Mandukya Upanishad</i>
3 state of consciousness	<i>Yogachudamani Upanishad</i>
Pranava as AUM/OM as Brahma	<i>Dhyānbindu Upanishad, Taittiriya Upanishad, Amritanaada Upanishad, Kshurikopanishad, Mandukya Upanishad, Patanjala Yoga sutra</i>
AUM/Pranava location	<i>Gheranda Samhita, Dhyānbindu Upanishad</i>

CONCLUSION:

To enhance mental health, people worldwide are turning towards *Yoga* and spiritual therapies. This can be effectively achieved through the correct and systematic chanting of *Mantras*. *Aumkara Mantra* is a non-invasive and cost-effective Yogic and spiritual practice that promotes Physical, Mental & Spiritual health and quality of life. It relieves various types of miseries and aids in the attainment of spiritual goals. The

scientific evidence supports its efficacy in decreasing stress levels by enhancing Galvanic Skin Response and reducing psychological distress. *Aumkara Mantra* meditation can be considered a valuable tool for enhancing physical, mental and spiritual well-being.

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